

Chemical Investigation of *Astercantha longifolia*, Nees (N.O. A. Canthaceae)

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Astercantha longifolia (Nees) (Syn. *Hygrophylla spinosa*, T. Anders) is found widely throughout India. The roots and seeds have been widely used in the indigenous system of medicine¹. Earlier workers^{2,3} have isolated lupeol and some minor components from the roots of this plant. The present work revealed the presence of stigmasterol to the extent of 0.1% besides lupeol, 0.3%, a straight chain ketone and a mixture of hydrocarbons from the whole plants.

Procedure.: The petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract, on removal of the solvent gave a semisolid substance which when extracted with methanol could be separated into two fractions viz., methanol-soluble and methanol-insoluble. The former was found to contain two substances on TLC over silica gel, which when separated by column chromatography over neutral alumina gave two substances (R_f value 0.7 and 0.6, toluene: ethylacetate = 4:6). The major fraction gave colourless needles, m.p. 212-213° (α)_D +28° in chloroform. This was found to be lupeol from its physical and chemical properties. The second fraction of the above chromatogram on crystallisation from 95% ethanol gave a colourless crystalline substance, C₃₀H₄₈O, m.p. 168° (α)_D -49° in chloroform, showed positive Liebermann's test (pink-green). The IR spectrum showed absorption at 3350 (hydroxyl), 1650, 975 and 805 cm⁻¹. It readily formed an acetate, m.p. 141° (α)_D -49° (CHCl₃). A solution of this substance in chloroform gave a deep brown colour with a solution of tetranitromethane. Bromination of its acetate gave a tetrabromoderivative, m.p. 204-205°. This substance was found to be identical with stigmasterol.

The methanol insoluble fraction of petroleum extract showed the presence of three compounds by TLC (R_f 0.85, 0.8 and 0.4, petroleum 60-80°, ethylacetate = 8:1). This mixture on chromatography on a column of neutral alumina grade I could be separated into three fractions, corresponding to the above R_f values. The easily eluted petroleum fraction gave a colourless substance on crystallisation from acetone-methanol having m.p. 70.72°. The IR spectrum of this did not show absorption for any functional group. The elemental analysis showed it to be hydrocarbons which on GLC were found to be a mixture of saturated straight chain hydrocarbons of various chain lengths of C₂₇-C₃₃, the odd carbon compounds predominating.

1. *Wealth of India*, CSIR, New Delhi, p. 351.

2. Govindachari, Nagarajan and Pal., *J. Sci. Industr. Res.* 72 16B, 1957.

3. Chatterjee and Srimani *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1957 34, 882.

The middle fraction on crystallisation from methanol-ethyl acetate gave a crystalline substance, m.p. 76-78° which analysed for $C_{12}H_{24}O$. The IR spectrum of this showed the presence of carbonyl group (1720 cm^{-1}). It did not give colour with tetranitromethane and Liebermann's test. It was optically inactive and did not respond to iodoform test, showing that the keto group is not attached to the terminal carbon atom.

The last fraction being in small yield was not worked out further.

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